

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

BY WISE JESTER

INSTRUCTION

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HOW TO USE IIB: GENERAL INSTRUCTION (v. 1.1)

IIB is a blind, humor-based computational change agent, which is made for emergence of flat, non-hierarchical experimental collaboration forms of professionals, who can behave as individuals, authors of collaborations, and their members. By applying humor, IIB shows to the users, if they have honestly graded the jokes, how they naturally perceive clashes and fracture under uncertainty, common in the processes of change and sudden hair-raising transformation events, when experimenting is the way to change the status-quo and achieve. Also, when the users are clustered in collaborations, IIB shows them a diversity of their qualities and needs as a group in situations of fracture, clash, experiment, and high uncertainty. IIB disrupts comfort zones and conventional ways of decision making by providing challenge, ease, and support.

And now the same, but in SIMPLER words:

IIB is a machine, which can show you how you think in a situation/process of uncertainty. You can find individuals and have a choice among several of them – just as they have towards groups of collaborating individuals. Both sides – independent professionals and collaborations in IIB – are beneficial to each other: they cover the needs in thinking change by relevant capacities and bring in complementary knowledge in a way that both sides learn something new. IIB is blind and it shows who you are as a set of capacities in thinking change, if you are an independent professional, and a set of collective needs in thinking change, if you are an author of a collaboration. IIB is designed to deliver such results that are mutually beneficial in a mid and long run, but are somewhat disrupting (read: “disturbing”) in a short run. IIB delivers change agents. Everybody can become a change agent for any group of people.

IIB is blind: it does not need to know your name, face, age, gender, social status, cultural and ethnic background, and things like that.

Values: facilitation of actual *de facto* collaborations; leading to more satisfied workers of any kind; nurturing and attracting hybrid competencies from the entire population or from your past, surprisingly; eradicating lies and hypocrisy in self-representation on both sides – individuals and groups of people; attracting smarties and retaining them, provided that the recipients possess some brains too.

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

Contact us

Log in

In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations ([INSTRUCTION](#)) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

FOR INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

As an independent professional, you may be anybody: curious sustainable doer with a broad knowledge horizon, specialist, operative worker, leader, freelancer, nerd, creator, misfit, intuitive introvert, or the one wishing changes but afraid to look stupid, or you may be involved in parallel projects and willing to get support or be willing to challenge yourself regularly. You create your user by going through “Begin as an independent professional”. A specific instruction about this precedes that process.

INSTRUCTION.

You are about to create an IIB-user as an individual. You will be able to find new collaborators for your projects, who will be compatible with you in many ways, create collaborations of your own or join those of the others. You will be able to see your strengths in dealing with uncertainties and transitions, show them to the others, and apply! You own your data, and it can be deleted by yourself.

Now, you will see some fun pictures to set the mood, and then you are invited to rate a series of jokes from 0 (not funny) to 5 (very funny). After that, you will be asked to select 5 competencies of your own: what you have studied, worked with, and have a passion for. These competencies will be associated with you to make you represented in the system, which is blind to your identification by name, status, age, gender, and other labels. You are represented by a set of your strengths and capacities, and the competencies which you can change. You decide if you want to create your own collaborations or join any exciting collaborations of the others. IIB empowers individual professionals and collaborations, based on their strengths, capacities, needs and competencies, encourages learning and emergence! Have fun!

SURE, SHOW ME THE JOKES!

experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

Here are some pictures to cheer you up! Just flip them through!

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

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Log in

If Tolstoy and Dostoevsky could have met, they would have written “War and Idiots”.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Rate 'Em All

11/36

In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations ([INSTRUCTION](#)) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

[Team Wise Jester](#)

[What IIB is](#)

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One man was cleaning his ear with a cotton swab but pressed too hard and reset himself to the factory settings.

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In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations ([INSTRUCTION](#)) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

DONE!

Result page

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is **coming up with alternatives**.

- While thinking, you are rather after **knowledge**.
- You tend to react immediately to **emotional signals**.
- You prefer working in **collectivistic environments**.

Hybrid innovation, Complex systems, Entrepreneurship, Regulation, Physics

capacities for transformation

- preferred comfort zones
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instantth. triggers
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
- deep-th. triggers
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

- FIND A NEW COLLABORATOR FOR ME
- FIND A NEW COLLABORATION FOR ME
- TAKE A RETAKE
- DELETE MY DATA

FOR INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

When your user is created, you may be passively available in the system to get contacted by the collaborations which would need your capacities and hybrid knowledge. You are visible 24/7/365(366)* until you decide to delete your data.

Find new collaborators to add into my collaboration from the entire system

Look Externally

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

RESULTS

you are visible this way to a collaboration which looks to itself that way

Needs of my collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with fear of difference and novelty.
Your collaboration may experience being too down-to-earth.
Your collaboration might be overlooking the socially accepted.
Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by pressuring the members.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in collectivistic environments.
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for imagination.
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: regulation, communication, hybrid innovation.
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, engineering.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is breaking the old things down faster.
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in high-pressure contexts.
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for solidarity with the others.
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: hybrid innovation.
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: complex systems, entrepreneurship, physics, music.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.
To balance your work style, this person prefers working in independent genre.
When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for solidarity with the others.
The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: hybrid innovation.
The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: engineering, complex systems, economics, social work.

PREVIOUS

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

FOR INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

Or you may act!

You may begin your own collaborations by using the blind functionalities of IIB which shall find for you other independent professionals, being helpful and constructively challenged to collaborate with you, if available to get involved into the experimental processes that you would wish to start despite the uncertainty on your way to your vision. Also, you may invite someone you know!

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

you promise to behave good

Here is a list of the competencies as knowledge areas which you may wish to see in the collaborators. The first competence you select will be preferential. The IIB system will look for at least 3 out of 5 competencies that you choose. Please, choose 5 competencies. You will also see how the found candidates can complement and disrupt your ways of thinking, working, acting, and reacting, with the competencies from your request. You will not see their names and any other labels. On seeing the results of your request, you will be able to introduce yourself to one, some, or all of them.

If you do not want to use this function, you can skip it on the page with the results and go to the page where you can add the concrete people you know by sending them invitations. They will be added into your collaboration that way. Of course, you can use the computational search another time.

To proceed, please, accept that you act on a good will, and you will not use the IIB system to cause any harm to any persons, collaborations, organizations, and any other individual and collective actors of professionals. You treat the proposed candidates with respect, no matter of their differences, situational circumstances, visions, plans and codes of behavior. By using the IIB system, you will not take any actions in breach of any legal agreements you are obliged to keep. The results, generated by IIB, shall not be used for any forms of dismissals. The use of IIB shall lead to hybridization of knowledge for lifelong learning, and to dynamic, peaceful, creative, and efficient flat collaboration processes of their members and authors.

Accept

Choose 5

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

PREVIOUS

NEXT

you must accept a smart contract to begin the automated blind operations by IIB, and you place your "order" here

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

*blindly, you see other people better,
and they may collaborate with you*

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **coming up with alternatives**.
 While thinking, you are rather after **knowledge**.
 You tend to react immediately to **emotional signals**.
 You prefer working in **collectivistic environments**.

PREVIOUS

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals**.
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim**.
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis**.
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics**.
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics**.

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals**.
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **imagination**.
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis**.
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, statistics**.
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics**.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals**.
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **solidarity with the others**.
 The main strength of this person is in **faster taking the new into practice**.
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, statistics**.
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, coding, robotics**.

PROCEED: INVITE BY EMAIL

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

You chose to add new members into your collaboration manually. By using this form, you can send invitations to them. On having received your invitation, the persons will have to create their users in the IIB system and generate individual results. Then, your collaboration shall get a new or updated visualization automatically. Please, mark below if the invited persons belong to your previous endeavors: if you are collaborating or have been involved in a common collaborative process, and so you wish to see them in your virtual collaboration here. If the persons are completely new to your previous endeavors, do not select that. You can always add new collaborators, previously unrelated to your endeavors.

Below, you see a brief introduction which will open your message. You conclude it with your own words. IIB is blind, so the persons will not be able to know for sure if the message belongs to you, although you may know each other. That is why, to give the persons a clue of the collaboration they are invited to join, you are kindly requested to complete your invitation.

The invited persons belong to my previous endeavors (we have been collaborating)

My invitation letter

Hello!

This is an invitation from the humor-based computational change agent Intellectual and Immaterial Bank (IIB) from one of your actual or previous colleagues. You are invited by them to join a new, virtual collaboration that they are creating. You are invited to accept this invitation and create your own user in the IIB system, which facilitates flat collaboration in high uncertainty and hybridization of competencies. You will be able to create your collaborations too. You own your data and can delete it by yourself.

You can read more about IIB here: <https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com/>

You can accept the invitation and create your user by going here:

The author of the collaboration wrote this to you:

Describe your vision here

Email of the individual professional whom you want to invite

SEND

PREVIOUS

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

**or you can manually invite someone you know
– to collaborate with you**

FOR INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONALS

Or you may actively look for any existing collaborations for you to join!

They will be challenging and giving to you, and you will have a common vision. You will be able to learn there, while being helpful.

Find new collaborations for me to join!

COMPETENCE

RESULTS

collaborations are visible this way to you, while you see yourself that way

This is you

PREVIOUS

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **structures and processes that are stuck**.
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members**.
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth**.
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, robotics**.
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, arts, hybrid innovation**.

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **structures and processes that are stuck**.
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **demanding clarity and plan**.
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **siloed thinking**.
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, robotics**.
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, arts, hybrid innovation**.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **fear of difference and novelty**.
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **pressuring the members**.
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth**.
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **math, robotics**.
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, arts, hybrid innovation**.

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

FOR AUTHORS OF COLLABORATIONS

As an author of a collaboration, you are an independent professional (see above), but you have a clear intention to experiment when you experience uncertainty in your collective: to get a holistic picture of its intellectual needs and competencies in change, increase hybridization of knowledge, disrupt its comfort zones in a way that nothing would collapse, build parallel collaborative processes, each of which being experimental, and bring in new blood.

You create your user by going through “Begin as an author of a collaboration”. A specific instruction about this precedes. First, you select a set of knowledge areas that characterize the collaboration you are starting, that is on behalf of your collaboration. You can change them later. Then, you enjoy the jokes and select your own knowledge spheres as your own competencies, because you are the author of this collaboration and you belong to it, just like all the other people you will add into it.

INSTRUCTION.

You are about to create your own collaboration of individual professionals, who will be dealing with uncertainty and change, and across diverse knowledge areas. First, select 5 competencies on behalf of your collaboration: what of the presented competencies and knowledge areas that your collaboration deals with. You can change them later. IIB will use those competencies and the visualization of your collaboration to present it to all the other users in the system.

Second, have fun! You will see some fun pictures to set the mood, and then you are invited to rate a series of jokes from 0 (not funny) to 5 (very funny). After that, you will be asked to select 5 competencies again, but this time of your own: what you have studied, worked with, and have a passion for. These competencies will be associated with you as an individual professional to make you represented in the system, which is blind to your name, status, age, gender, and other labels. Neither the names of your collaborations are needed. IIB is blind.

In your cabinet, you will find a few tools to invite new members into your collaboration and see its visualization. You can invite the new members by invitation if you know who you want to see in your collaboration, or you can use IIB to propose to you entirely new people, based on their capacities and competencies. You can create more collaborations, which may have different natures and purposes! You decide and direct the processes.

I UNDERSTAND. PROCEED

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

Contact us

Log in

How would you introduce your collaboration to others?

Name of my collaboration

A brief description or slogan

NEXT STEP

In blindness to facial data, individual professionals and collaborations ([INSTRUCTION](#)) may enjoy humor and see how they normally think in situations of experiment and fracture between the old and the new, find each other directly, and move on to their goals. Read [Terms of Use and Privacy](#).

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

Select 5 competencies on behalf of your collaboration: what of the presented areas does your collaboration deal with?
IIB will use those to present your collaboration to all the other users in the system.

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

DONE!

Here are some pictures to cheer you up! Just flip them through!

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

Contact us

Log in

The claim that rock music causes cruelty and uncontrollable aggression in people can be easily refuted with one blow to the head with a shovel.

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BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

[Team Wise Jester](#)

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Aliens, observing humans: What are they celebrating? – Their planet made a full circle around their star. – I told you they are not intelligent.

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BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

DONE!

AnyTwelve (1 members)

- FIND COLLABORATORS
- SETTINGS
- TAKE A RETAKE
- BACK

Your capacities

Needs of your collaboration

Collaboration consists of two or more individuals. Please, use the proposed options to the right for adding new individuals into your collaboration. When one and more are invited and become users in IIB, the system will generate for you a visualization of your collaboration. The invited individuals will be able to see their own results and the visualization of the collaboration. You can create more collaborations for the different purposes that you may have.

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.** While thinking, you are rather after imagination. You tend to react immediately to **social signals.** You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

Your collaboration may have a challenge with
 Your collaboration may experience
 Your collaboration might be overlooking
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by

now, this is you as an author of your own collaboration

- preferred comfort zones**
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instant triggers**
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
- deep triggers**
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

- disruption of comfort**
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore**
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How the others feel
 - Siloed thinking
- intellectual depth**
 - Being too dispersed
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
 - Fear of difference and novelty
 - Seeing the big picture
- needs in transformation**
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the members
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

FOR AUTHORS OF COLLABORATIONS

When your user is created, you will see your own intellectual and immaterial capital in the context of fracture and change, and you will be asked to add members into your collaboration, because a collaboration consists of two and more professionals. You are provided with the options how to do that: either by blind computation of IIB or by manual invitations.

AnyTwelve (1 members)

- FIND COLLABORATORS
- SETTINGS
- TAKE A RETAKE
- BACK

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon**. While thinking, you are rather after imagination. You tend to react immediately to social signals. You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts**.

Needs of your collaboration

Collaboration consists of two or more individuals. Please, use the proposed options to the right for adding new individuals into your collaboration. When one and more are invited and become users in IIB, the system will generate for you a visualization of your collaboration. The invited individuals will be able to see their own results and the visualization of the collaboration. You can create more collaborations for the different purposes that you may have.

Your collaboration may have a challenge with
 Your collaboration may experience
 Your collaboration might be overlooking
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by

de facto, collaboration takes two or more, so now you must act!

- preferred comfort zones**
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instant th. triggers**
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
- deep th. triggers**
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
- capacities for transformation**
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

- disruption of comfort**
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore**
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How the others feel
 - Siloed thinking
- intellectual depth**
 - Being too dispersed
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
 - Fear of difference and novelty
 - Seeing the big picture
- needs in transformation**
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the members
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

FIND NEW COLLABORATORS COMPUTATIONALLY

ADD NEW COLLABORATORS BY INVITATIONS

you promise to behave good

Here is a list of the competencies as knowledge areas which you may wish to see in the collaborators. The first competence you select will be preferential. The IIB system will look for at least 3 out of 5 competencies that you choose. Please, choose 5 competencies. You will also see how the found candidates can complement and disrupt your ways of thinking, working, acting, and reacting, with the competencies from your request. You will not see their names and any other labels. On seeing the results of your request, you will be able to introduce yourself to one, some, or all of them.

If you do not want to use this function, you can skip it on the page with the results and go to the page where you can add the concrete people you know by sending them invitations. They will be added into your collaboration that way. Of course, you can use the computational search another time.

To proceed, please, accept that you act on a good will, and you will not use the IIB system to cause any harm to any persons, collaborations, organizations, and any other individual and collective actors of professionals. You treat the proposed candidates with respect, no matter of their differences, situational circumstances, visions, plans and codes of behavior. By using the IIB system, you will not take any actions in breach of any legal agreements you are obliged to keep. The results, generated by IIB, shall not be used for any forms of dismissals. The use of IIB shall lead to hybridization of knowledge for lifelong learning, and to dynamic, peaceful, creative, and efficient flat collaboration processes of their members and authors.

Accept

Choose 5

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

BACK

NEXT

you must accept a smart contract to begin the automated blind operations by IIB, and you place your "order" here

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

FIND NEW COLLABORATORS COMPUTATIONALLY

ADD NEW COLLABORATORS BY INVITATIONS

blindness in action

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

PREVIOUS

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **imagination.**
 The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, statistics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**
 While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**
 The main strength of this person is in **breaking the old things down faster.**
 The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**

ALTERNATIVELY: INVITE BY EMAIL

Find or invite new individual professionals into my collaborations!

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

FIND NEW COLLABORATORS COMPUTATIONALLY

ADD NEW COLLABORATORS BY INVITATIONS

You chose to add new members into your collaboration manually. By using this form, you can send invitations to them. On having received your invitation, the persons will have to create their users in the IIB system and generate individual results. Then, your collaboration shall get a new or updated visualization automatically. Please, mark below if the invited persons belong to your previous endeavors: if you are collaborating or have been involved in a common collaborative process, and so you wish to see them in your virtual collaboration here. If the persons are completely new to your previous endeavors, do not select that. You can always add new collaborators, previously unrelated to your endeavors.

Below, you see a brief introduction which will open your message. You conclude it with your own words. IIB is blind, so the persons will not be able to know for sure if the message belongs to you, although you may know each other. That is why, to give the persons a clue of the collaboration they are invited to join, you are kindly requested to complete your invitation.

The invited persons belong to my previous endeavors (we have been collaborating)

My invitation letter

Hello!

This is an invitation from the humor-based computational change agent Intellectual and Immaterial Bank (IIB) from one of your actual or previous colleagues. You are invited by them to join a new, virtual collaboration that they are creating. You are invited to accept this invitation and create your own user in the IIB system, which facilitates flat collaboration in high uncertainty and hybridization of competencies. You will be able to create your collaborations too. You own your data and can delete it by yourself.

You can read more about IIB here: <https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com/>

You can accept the invitation and create your user by going here:

The author of the collaboration wrote this to you:

Describe your vision here

SEND

PREVIOUS

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

or you can manually invite someone you know, with whom you collaborate de facto

FOR AUTHORS OF COLLABORATIONS

Your collaboration may be passively available in the IIB computational system to get contacted by any new, unknown to you independent professionals, who are helpful and wish to be challenged.

In IIB, nobody “fits” anybody, because “fitting in” does not exist in real life. We all move in time and progress in variations of scenarios of our individual, highly complex adaptive plans, based on unique schemata in our minds. If you are active, today you are not the same as yesterday, when you seemingly “fitted in” somewhere. The favorite question by the traditional “Human Resource” industry and the most lunatic question a conscious professional can receive is “What do you see yourself in 5 years?” In contrast, high-tech environments – in social robotics or virtual labs – are holacratic, value time, and have the farthest horizon of 3 years.

IIB is about mutual contribution, challenge and a shared vision between the sides, guaranteed by blindness, science, informed choices, empowerment of every node in the network, and its large scale. In IIB, you have no mediators: nobody interprets you.

Actively, as an author of a collaboration – and you can have as many collaborations as you need – you can search for any new independent professionals on your own: from the entire IIB population, “externally”, or from any of your previous endeavors and their endeavors, “internally”, provided those professionals happen to be in the system as its users.

AnyEight (2 members)

- FIND COLLABORATORS
- LOOK INTERNALLY
- LOOK EXTERNALLY
- MEMBER LIST
- SETTINGS
- TAKE A RETAKE
- BACK

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon**.
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination**.
 You tend to react immediately to **social signals**.
 You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts**.

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck**.
 Your collaboration may experience **being too dispersed**.
 Your collaboration might be overlooking the **socially accepted**.
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by **pressuring the members**.

so, now you are two and can be more!

- preferred comfort zones**
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instant triggers**
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
- depth triggers**
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
- capacities for transformation**
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

- disruption of comfort**
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore**
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How the others feel
 - Siloed thinking
 - Being too dispersed
 - Ignoring uniqueness
- intellectual depth**
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
 - Fear of difference and novelty
 - Seeing the big picture
- needs in transformation**
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the members
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

Find new collaborations for me to join!

COMPETENCE

RESULTS

This is you

Your strongest capacity for making change is **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**
 While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**
 You tend to react immediately to **emotional signals.**
 You prefer working in contexts with **high uncertainty.**

while you are taking actions, your collaboration(s) is (are) already visible that way to any new to you independent professionals, who may choose yours among other collaborations

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **obvious needs in new, previously unknown ideas.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **accountability and transparency.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **user experience, writing.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **social work, entrepreneurship, xr.**

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **seeing the big picture.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **demanding clarity and plan.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **ignoring uniqueness.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **hybrid innovation, complex systems.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **entrepreneurship, physics, music.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The highest need in change of this collaboration is **seeing the big picture.**
 What would be comfortable to you in this collaboration is **demanding clarity and plan.**
 This collaboration has an intellectual challenge in **being too down-to-earth.**
 The competencies, which this collaboration has for you, are: **hybrid innovation, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which you can develop at this collaboration, are: **economics, regulation, coding.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

PREVIOUS

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

Find new collaborators to add into my collaboration from the entire system

you use IIB actively

Look Externally

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

RESULTS

don't forget to be a good person

This is a contract between you as an author of a collaboration and IIB.

Please, accept that you act on a good will, and you will not use the IIB system to cause any harm to any persons, collaborations, organizations, and any other individual and collective actors of professionals. You treat the proposed candidates with respect, no matter of their differences, situational circumstances, visions, plans and codes of behavior. By using the IIB system, you will not take any actions in breach of any legal agreements you are obliged to keep. The results, generated by IIB, shall not be used for any forms of dismissals. The use of IIB shall lead to hybridization of knowledge for lifelong learning, and to dynamic, peaceful, creative, and efficient flat collaboration processes of their members and authors.

The IIB system shall look now among all the professionals as individuals, who are registered here and are available to get involved into collaborations. They will be represented in visualizations of their capacities and strengths to handle uncertainty and change, along with at least 3 out of 5 competencies as knowledge areas which you request to look for. The IIB system will find those candidates who can complement and creatively disrupt your collaboration in thinking, working, acting, and reacting, with the competencies from your request. You will not see their names and any other labels. On seeing the results of your request, you will be able to introduce yourself to one, some, or all of them.

Below is a list of the competencies as knowledge areas which you may wish to see in the collaborators for the IIB system to find for you. The first competence you select will be preferential. The IIB system will look for at least 3 out of 5 competencies that you choose. Please, choose 5 competencies.

Accept

Choose 5

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Arts
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication

BACK

you must accept a smart contract to use the blindness of IIB, and you place your "order" here

NEXT

Find new collaborators to add into my collaboration from the entire system

Look Externally

THE COMPETENCIES THAT I AM LOOKING FOR

RESULTS

Needs of my collaboration

now, you go and look blindly

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck.**
 Your collaboration may experience **being too dispersed.**
 Your collaboration might be **overlooking the socially accepted.**
 Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by **pressuring the members.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **faster taking the new into practice.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **collectivistic environments.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **statistics, physics, engineering.**

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **high-pressure contexts.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **imagination.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **xr, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering.**

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

and people are blindly available

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **breaking the old things down faster.**
 To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **contexts with high uncertainty.**
 When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **focused aim.**
 The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics.**
 The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, math, engineering.**

PREVIOUS

Click "Finish" to complete

FINISH

FOR BOTH

IIB is blind. Introduce yourself when you have found interesting independent professionals or collaborations. Even if they happen to know you, they will not know you in the IIB system until you introduce yourself. Be creative and brief, but concrete and honest, when you wish to involve or join. IIB has already considered much, including your imagination, to propose you those who you see on your screen. They are brought to you with some surprises, based on your own results. Moreover, both sides, being compatible by a set of surprises, perspectively in a mid/long run, are encouraged to learn new knowledge mutually, on having their collaboration established.

If available for collaboration, any professional can be reached. It can be someone completely new to the requesting side: that happens when the requesting side chooses to look “externally”. There can also be found someone already known from before, that is from any previous endeavors of the requesting side back in the past, by a certain set of surprises. If this is the case, you might meet your former colleagues, for example. You may see them in a new, unexpected light, and discover in them some new capacities, which you previously overlooked: that happens when the requesting side chooses to look “internally”. The “previous endeavors” are created by the independent professionals directly, entirely bottom up, when they choose to invite into their collaborations someone that they know, manually, bypass the blind options.

You have several options to (re-)structure and lead your collaborations, which you can have as many as you need, for different purposes. You can manage your data and settings. You own your data, which you can delete at any time, including your collaborations. On the right side of the screen, you see the options for taking actions; on the left, the menu of what you have done.

FOR BOTH

By creating a user, you confirm that you act on good will, and you will not use the IIB system to cause any harm to any persons, collaborations, organizations, and any other individual and collective actors of professionals. By using the IIB system, you will not take any actions in breach of any legal agreements you are obliged to keep. You are obliged to respect the rights of others, including their privacy and intellectual property rights. You are also obliged to never violate any third-party rights.

Through the IIB system, you can send messages and share information when you introduce yourself and/or your collaboration, and when you write invitations. Information and content that you insert will be sent to the user that you interact with in the IIB system. You do not undertake any activities that may abuse, harm, interfere with, or disrupt the functioning of the IIB system. You do not copy, modify, distribute, transmit or otherwise use any data elements and components of the IIB system, unless they are directly designed to be dynamically responding to your data when you fairly use the IIB system as its user of for the purposes the IIB services are made for.

The use of IIB shall lead to hybridization of knowledge for lifelong learning and its visionary implementation in action, production, reveal and application of change thinking, and to novel, dynamic, creative, peaceful, and efficient collaborative processes of their authors and members. You provide yours and true information when you interact with other users in the IIB system. The information you state cannot be fraudulent, false, or misleading. You also grade the jokes honestly. You agree to be a person of integrity.

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com/>

2010, 2017, 2019/20, 2021...

**WISE
JESTER**

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***Genially,
Anna Andreyevna Zaytseva***